

An assessment of lecturers ability in transferring the necessary skills in classroom: The College of Technological Studies, Kuwait as a case study

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Abstract

Recently, there is a considerable gap between what is learned in the classroom and the real life context of vocational and technical students' present and future workplace. This problem mostly occur in developing countries where lecturers in vocational and technical education have limited knowledge and experience of the real practice of industry and thus their experience is limited within the bounders on their institutions. This paper examine whether lecturers take into consideration those skills mostly needed by industry in their classes. In other words, do lecturers know the skills needed for today's workplace? The study also examines the degree of industrialist's involvement with vocational and technical lecturers in determining the types of knowledge, skills and attitudes that need to be stressed in the classroom. The study would consists of: a review of the related literature; a questionnaire that would be distributed to a sample of lecturers at the College of Technological Studies; Personal interviews with the head of the department; dean of industrial liaison offices; and the department trainee's direct supervisors in local industry. This paper would conclude that lecturers must emphasis and develop the mostly needed knowledge, skills and attitudes by industries in their classes, otherwise industries would heavily depend on expatriates for years to come.